

Tracking the Pulse of the Ocean

Communication & Dissemination strategy

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1 Executive summary

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy outlines how the BioGeoSea project ensures the visibility, accessibility, and uptake of its activities and results throughout the project lifetime.

BioGeoSea addresses key challenges in biogeochemical ocean observing by enhancing Essential Ocean Variables, improving data quality and integration, and developing indicators that support scientific understanding and informed decision-making in the context of ocean change.

The strategy clearly distinguishes between communication and dissemination activities while treating both as complementary and coordinated elements of project impact. Communication focuses on raising awareness, explaining relevance, and engaging broader audiences, whereas dissemination targets expert, policy, industrial, and operational communities to enable uptake and reuse of validated results. All activities are implemented as a consortium-wide effort, coordinated centrally and aligned with the project's vision, mission, and key messages.

BioGeoSea uses a combination of digital, scientific, and stakeholder-oriented channels. The project website and its evolving Knowledge Hub serve as the central access point for information and outputs, supported by open-access dissemination through Zenodo, targeted use of LinkedIn, mailing lists, community newsletters, events, and visual outreach materials such as videos and flyers. Close collaboration with sister projects and structured interaction with policy processes further strengthen coherence and reach.

Communication and dissemination activities are monitored using qualitative and quantitative metrics, allowing the consortium to refine approaches over time. Through its website and Knowledge Hub, open-access publications, targeted LinkedIn communication, stakeholder engagement, explanatory videos on the four biogeochemical phenomena, and policy-oriented outputs, BioGeoSea ensures that its work on Essential Ocean Variables and ocean indicators reaches scientific, policy, industrial, and societal audiences. This structured yet flexible approach supports the long-term visibility and uptake of project results and contributes to strengthening biogeochemical ocean observing beyond the project duration.

2 Introduction

Effective communication and dissemination are essential to maximise the impact of research and innovation activities funded under Horizon Europe. Beyond generating scientific results, projects are expected to ensure transparency, accessibility, and uptake of knowledge by relevant scientific, policy, industrial, and societal audiences.

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy defines the principles, objectives, structures, and workflows guiding communication and dissemination activities in the BioGeoSea project. It provides a common framework for the consortium to ensure coherent, coordinated, and audience-appropriate engagement throughout the project lifetime.

The strategy is a living document that supports adaptive implementation. It complements other project-level strategies, including stakeholder engagement and exploitation planning, and provides guidance for aligning communication and dissemination activities with BioGeoSea's scientific goals, societal relevance, and Horizon Europe requirements.

3 Project overview

BioGeoSea – Enhancing Biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables for European and Global Assessments – is a Horizon Europe project addressing the growing need for reliable, integrated, and policy-relevant biogeochemical ocean observing. As the ocean responds to climate change and increasing human pressures, processes such as ocean acidification, ocean deoxygenation, and changes in carbon cycling are intensifying, with significant consequences for marine ecosystems, climate regulation, and socio-economic activities.

Despite their importance, many biogeochemical changes remain insufficiently observed and unevenly integrated across observing systems. BioGeoSea responds to this challenge by strengthening the observation, validation, and modelling of biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables (BGC EOVs) and by improving the coherence and usability of resulting data and products.

The project focuses on four interconnected biogeochemical phenomena: ocean acidification, ocean deoxygenation, the biological carbon pump, and greenhouse gas fluxes. Across these areas, BioGeoSea advances data quality, harmonisation, and integration, and develops indicators that enable consistent assessments across regions and time scales.

Beyond scientific and technical developments, BioGeoSea works closely with research infrastructures, international initiatives, policymakers, and blue economy actors. This close collaboration ensures that project outputs are aligned with user needs, contribute to standards and best practices, and support informed decision-making at European and global levels.

Through its integrated approach, BioGeoSea aims to strengthen Europe's contribution to global biogeochemical ocean observing and to provide the knowledge base needed for sustainable ocean management in a changing climate.

4 Project vision, mission and slogan

4.1 Vision

An integrated observing system delivering timely, transparent biogeochemical knowledge for society, the blue economy, science, and policy — enabling informed decisions.

This vision expresses BioGeoSea's long-term ambition to strengthen the role of biogeochemical ocean observations in addressing societal, environmental, and economic challenges related to ocean change.

4.2 Mission

BioGeoSea enhances biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables, integrates observing systems, advances data products, improves models, and develops ocean indicators. We

deliver the knowledge and tools needed to protect the future of our blue planet by turning trusted data into insight that enables the development of solutions for sustainable ocean management.

The mission defines BioGeoSea's concrete contribution to improving ocean observing and knowledge generation, forming the basis for all communication and dissemination objectives outlined in this strategy.

4.3 Slogan

Tracking the Pulse of the Ocean

The project slogan complements the vision and mission by providing a concise and accessible expression of BioGeoSea's core idea. It is primarily used in communication-oriented contexts, such as the project website, visual materials, and outreach activities, while remaining consistent with the project's scientific objectives.

5 Definitions and scope

To ensure a shared understanding across the consortium and with external stakeholders, BioGeoSea distinguishes between *communication* and *dissemination* activities in line with Horizon Europe guidance. Both are essential and complementary elements of the project's impact strategy.

5.1 Communication

Communication refers to activities aimed at promoting the project, its objectives, and its overall relevance to a broad range of audiences beyond the scientific community. In BioGeoSea, communication focuses on explaining why biogeochemical ocean observing matters, highlighting project progress, and raising awareness of the societal and environmental challenges addressed by the project.

Typical communication activities include:

- Content published on the BioGeoSea website and social media
- News items, visual materials, and outreach content
- Communication around selected project milestones, events, and field activities that are relevant for broader audiences

The primary goal of communication is to increase awareness and understanding of the importance of measuring and understanding ocean biogeochemistry for climate, the blue economy, and ocean health, while also highlighting BioGeoSea and its contribution to biogeochemical ocean observing and sustainable ocean management.

5.2 Dissemination

Dissemination refers to the targeted sharing of BioGeoSea results, knowledge, and outputs with specific expert and stakeholder audiences who can directly use, build upon, or integrate these results into their own work. In BioGeoSea, dissemination activities are closely linked to scientific outputs, technical developments, and project deliverables related to biogeochemical ocean observing.

Typical dissemination activities include:

- Public deliverables, reports, and policy-relevant documents
- Contributions to standards, observing systems, and international initiatives
- Scientific publications and conference contributions

The primary goal of dissemination is to enable uptake, reuse, and long-term impact of BioGeoSea results within scientific, policy, and operational contexts.

5.3 Scope and interplay

Communication and dissemination in BioGeoSea are closely interconnected. Communication activities create awareness and contextual understanding of biogeochemical ocean observing, while dissemination ensures that concrete results reach the audiences capable of applying them. Together, they form an integrated approach that supports transparency, stakeholder engagement, and the effective transfer of knowledge throughout the project lifecycle.

6 Objectives of communication and dissemination

The communication and dissemination activities of BioGeoSea aim to maximise the visibility, understanding, and uptake of the project's work and results. The objectives outlined below guide the selection of target audiences, messages, channels, and workflows throughout the project lifecycle.

6.1 Communication objectives

The communication objectives of BioGeoSea are to:

- Raise awareness of the importance of biogeochemical ocean observing for understanding ocean change and supporting sustainable ocean management.
- Clearly explain the project's vision, mission, and scientific approach to non-expert and mixed audiences.
- Highlight project progress, selected milestones, events, and field activities in a transparent and accessible way.
- Strengthen the visibility of BioGeoSea within the European and international ocean observing landscape.
- Support engagement with stakeholders by providing timely, understandable, and relevant information.

6.2 Dissemination objectives

The dissemination objectives of BioGeoSea are to:

- Ensure that BioGeoSea results, methods, and data products reach relevant scientific, technical, policy-oriented, and industrial audiences.
- Enable uptake and reuse of BioGeoSea outputs within ocean observing systems, research infrastructures, modelling frameworks, and applied contexts.
- Support industrial partners, service providers, and potential investors by making relevant results and indicators visible, understandable, and reusable where appropriate.

- Contribute to the development and harmonisation of standards and best practices for biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables.
- Support evidence-based decision-making by making validated results available in appropriate formats.

7 Key messages

The key messages of BioGeoSea translate the project's vision, mission, and objectives into clear narratives that can be consistently communicated and disseminated across audiences and channels. They are structured into core project messages and topic-specific messages.

7.1 Core project messages

The following core messages apply across all communication and dissemination activities and provide a coherent overarching narrative for BioGeoSea:

- **Biogeochemical ocean observing is essential for understanding and responding to ocean change.**
Changes in ocean chemistry, oxygen levels, and carbon cycling directly affect marine ecosystems, climate regulation, and human activities. Reliable observing systems are critical to detect, understand, and anticipate these changes.
- **BioGeoSea strengthens biogeochemical Essential Ocean Variables by improving data quality, integration, and usability.**
The project enhances observing systems, data products, and indicators to close critical knowledge gaps and enable consistent assessments across regions and time scales.
- **Better data enables better decisions.**
By turning trusted biogeochemical data into actionable knowledge, BioGeoSea develops indicators and data products designed to be usable by stakeholders and decision-makers, supporting practical application in environmental management, policy development, and operational contexts.
- **Integration and collaboration are key to impact.**
BioGeoSea brings together scientific communities, research infrastructures, stakeholders, and international initiatives to improve coherence, interoperability, and uptake of biogeochemical ocean observing.
- **BioGeoSea contributes to European and global ocean observing efforts.**
The project aligns with and supports broader frameworks and initiatives, strengthening Europe's role in global assessments and long-term ocean observation.

7.2 Topic-specific messages

In addition to the core project messages, BioGeoSea addresses several key biogeochemical phenomena that are central to understanding ocean change. Topic-specific messages allow the project to tailor communication and dissemination activities to particular results, audiences, and contexts while remaining consistent with the overall project narrative.

Ocean Acidification

Ocean acidification is a direct consequence of increased oceanic uptake of anthropogenic CO₂ and poses a significant risk to marine ecosystems and ecosystem services.

BioGeoSea improves the observation, validation, and interpretation of acidification-related biogeochemical variables to support consistent assessments across regions and time scales.

Enhanced indicators and data products help track acidification trends and support policy-relevant ocean health assessments.

Ocean Deoxygenation

Declining oxygen levels in the ocean, driven primarily by warming and changing circulation patterns, affect marine life, biogeochemical cycles, and ecosystem functioning.

BioGeoSea strengthens deoxygenation-related observing capacities by improving data integration and comparability across observing platforms.

The project supports better understanding of oxygen dynamics and their links to climate change and human pressures.

Biological Carbon Pump

The biological carbon pump plays a central role in regulating Earth's climate by transporting carbon from the surface ocean to deeper layers.

BioGeoSea advances the observation and modelling of biological carbon pump processes through improved biogeochemical indicators and data products.

These efforts contribute to more robust estimates of oceanic carbon uptake and sequestration.

Greenhouse Gas Fluxes

Ocean-atmosphere exchanges of greenhouse gases influence both climate feedbacks and mitigation efforts.

BioGeoSea enhances the observing and assessment of greenhouse gas fluxes by improving data quality, integration, and model representation.

The resulting products support more reliable regional and global greenhouse gas assessments.

8 Target audiences

BioGeoSea engages with a broad and diverse set of stakeholders across science, infrastructure, policy, industry, and society. Target audiences are grouped according to their roles in biogeochemical ocean observing, data use, policy uptake, and public engagement. Communication and dissemination activities are tailored to these groups to ensure relevance, uptake, and long-term impact.

8.1 Scientific and Expert Communities

Scientific and expert communities play a central role in shaping requirements, advancing methodologies, developing indicators, and contributing to best practices in biogeochemical ocean observing.

Key stakeholders include international science–policy interfaces, scientific coordination bodies, global observing initiatives, such as the IPCC, IPBES, GCOS, GOOS and its panels and initiatives (e.g. IOCCP, BioEco Panel), EuroGOOS, SCOR, OBPS, the UN Ocean Decade OceanPredict Programme, SOCOM, SOLAS, the Global Carbon Project, and related EU-funded projects.

Engagement with these communities focuses primarily on dissemination, ensuring that BioGeoSea results contribute to scientific assessments, observing frameworks, and international best practices, while selected communication activities support visibility and awareness.

8.2 Observing networks, monitoring bodies, and research infrastructures

Observing networks and research infrastructures are essential for sustained data collection, sensor validation, interoperability, and long-term continuity of biogeochemical ocean observing.

Relevant stakeholders include EuroGOOS Task Teams, networks of observing platforms (e.g. OceanSITES, SOCONET), European Research Infrastructures and ERICs (such as Euro-Argo, ICOS, EMSO, GO-SHIP, JERICO, EuroFleets), OceanOPS, METS-RCN, national monitoring programmes and research vessels, and satellite observing bodies including ESA.

Engagement with these actors is strongly dissemination-oriented, focusing on technical results, standards, indicators, and data integration, while communication supports coordination and awareness across networks.

8.3 Data infrastructures and product developers

Data infrastructures and product developers ensure the accessibility, interoperability, integration, and long-term usability of biogeochemical data and indicators.

Key stakeholders include global and regional data products and databases such as GO2DAT, GLODAP, SOCAT, MEMENTO, CARIMED, IMDOS, EMODnet (particularly Chemistry and Physics), SeaDataNet, ODIS, national data centres, and the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS).

Dissemination activities target these groups to support the uptake of BioGeoSea results into data products, services, and operational systems, while communication helps highlight availability and relevance.

8.4 European and international policy, governance, and funding bodies

Policy, governance, and funding bodies are critical for ensuring policy relevance, alignment with regulatory frameworks, and long-term legacy beyond the project duration.

Stakeholders include European Commission Directorates-General and Executive Agencies, national ministries, MSFD authorities, Regional Sea Conventions, ICES, IOC/UNESCO, WMO, JPI Oceans, high-level international agendas (e.g. G7 initiatives), and funding agencies and ERA networks.

Engagement combines communication (to explain relevance and implications) and dissemination (to provide evidence, indicators, and validated results that support assessments and decision-making).

8.5 Blue economy and industry actors

Blue economy and industry actors require reliable indicators, data products, and models to support operational decisions, risk assessments, and investment planning.

Relevant stakeholders include fisheries and aquaculture (including bivalve aquaculture), shipping and cruise tourism, eco-tourism operators, marine carbon removal companies, offshore wind and marine energy, oil and gas, desalination companies, insurance providers, technical inspection companies, consultancy firms, and international organisations such as FAO.

Dissemination activities focus on making relevant results visible, understandable, and reusable for applied contexts, while communication supports awareness and dialogue with industrial stakeholders and potential investors.

8.6 Civil society, NGOs, and communication stakeholders

Civil society organisations and communication stakeholders are essential for public engagement, ocean literacy, and broader societal awareness of ocean change.

This group includes NGOs working on climate, biodiversity, and ocean health, science communicators, ocean literacy initiatives, blue-economy networks, media and outreach organisations, and the general public.

Engagement with these audiences is primarily communication-oriented, focusing on accessible narratives, indicators, and visual materials that explain the relevance of biogeochemical ocean observing to society.

8.7 Communication vs. dissemination mapping

Table 1 summarises the primary mode of engagement for each audience group:

Table 1. Target audiences and their primary communication and dissemination focus in BioGeoSea

Audience Group	Communication	Dissemination
Scientific and expert communities	✓	✓✓
Observing networks, monitoring bodies, and research Infrastructures	✓	✓✓
Data infrastructures and product developers	✓	✓✓
European and international policy, governance, and funding bodies	✓✓	✓✓
Blue economy and industry actors	✓✓	✓✓
Civil society, NGOs, and communication stakeholders	✓✓	-

✓✓ = primary focus ; ✓ = secondary focus ; - = not applicable

9 Communication and dissemination channels

9.1 Digital communication channels

Digital channels form the backbone of BioGeoSea's communication activities and provide continuous, open access to project information.

The BioGeoSea website¹ serves as the central communication hub. It provides information on project objectives, structure, partners, news and events, and hosts a comprehensive library of publicly available deliverables, publications, policy briefs, and communication materials.

The website's Knowledge Hub is designed as a dynamic section that will grow over the course of the project. As BioGeoSea progresses and produces new results, indicators, and materials, the Knowledge Hub will be continuously expanded to reflect the evolving state of knowledge generated by the project.

Public deliverables and selected milestones are deposited in Zenodo, which serves as the central repository for BioGeoSea outputs (BioGeoSea Zenodo Community²).

Zenodo is used to:

- Assign persistent DOIs to deliverables and selected milestones
- Ensure version control and long-term accessibility
- Host additional dissemination materials such as conference papers, presentations, posters, and related outputs, where decided by the respective first authors

The project website links all public deliverables directly to their Zenodo DOIs, ensuring traceability, citability, and consistency between platforms.

9.2 Social media and mailing lists

LinkedIn is the only social media channel used by BioGeoSea. It is employed in a targeted manner to share selected project news and events, advertise publicly available deliverables and selected milestones, and highlight publications, videos, and outreach materials. Only content that is relevant for broader audiences and publicly accessible is promoted via social media.

In addition, the project consortium mailing list is used to coordinate internal communication. Where appropriate and in collaboration with relevant networks and initiatives, project information may also be shared through external community mailing lists and distribution channels to reach interested scientific and stakeholder audiences. Similarly, project updates may be submitted to established external newsletters, such as the EuroGOOS newsletter or the European Marine Board newsletter, subject to the respective editorial policies, in order to reach audiences beyond the immediate project network.

¹ <https://biogeosea.eu>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/biogeosea/>

9.3 Scientific and professional dissemination channels

Scientific and professional channels are central to the dissemination of BioGeoSea results to expert audiences.

These channels include peer-reviewed open-access scientific publications, contributions to conferences, workshops, and scientific meetings, technical reports, public deliverables, policy-relevant documents (e.g. policy briefs or policy papers), and contributions to international initiatives, observing systems, and best-practice platforms.

All dissemination activities comply with open-access requirements and, where applicable, make use of persistent identifiers and trusted repositories.

9.4 Stakeholder, policy, and coordination channels

Targeted channels are used to engage policy bodies, research infrastructures, industry actors, and coordination initiatives.

BioGeoSea maintains close interaction with the European Commission Project Officer, ensuring that important project information, progress, and relevant developments are shared in a timely and transparent manner.

The project also aims for close collaboration with sister projects addressing related topics. This includes regular coordination meetings, alignment of key messages, and mutual amplification of communication activities, for example through commenting on and reposting relevant LinkedIn content. These activities support coherence and visibility across related European initiatives.

9.5 Visual and outreach materials

Visual and outreach materials support both communication and dissemination by making complex scientific content more accessible to diverse audiences.

BioGeoSea will develop short explanatory videos of approximately two to five minutes for each of the four biogeochemical phenomena addressed by the project. These videos explain the underlying challenges, the role of Essential Ocean Variables and indicators, and how ocean observing supports sustainable ocean management, including BioGeoSea's specific contribution.

In addition, flyers and other printed materials providing accessible information on Essential Ocean Variables, indicators, and the addressed phenomena are produced. Visual and outreach materials are used at events and meetings and are made available via the BioGeoSea website.

10 Communication and dissemination workflows

This section describes how communication and dissemination activities are operationally implemented in BioGeoSea. The workflows ensure that relevant project outputs, activities, and developments are communicated and disseminated in a timely, coordinated, and audience-appropriate manner.

10.1 Workflow for project results, deliverables, and milestones

Project results, deliverables, and milestones are reviewed to identify those that are relevant for communication and/or dissemination beyond the consortium.

Public deliverables and selected milestones are:

- Reviewed internally by the responsible partners and, where appropriate, by the project coordinator or Steering Committee
- Deposited in Zenodo to ensure persistent identification, version control, and open access
- Linked from the project website, including direct references to the corresponding Zenodo DOIs

Selected deliverables and milestones that are relevant for broader audiences are additionally promoted via communication channels such as the project website, LinkedIn, and mailing lists.

Not all milestones are communicated publicly; communication focuses on those milestones that provide added value for external audiences, contribute to broader understanding of biogeochemical ocean observing, or mark significant scientific or strategic progress within the project. Milestones that represent internal development steps, preparatory work towards deliverables, or intermediate stages of scientific publications are generally not communicated separately in order to ensure coherence of results and to avoid conflicts with publication and citation practices.

10.2 Workflow for scientific publications and conference contributions

Scientific publications and conference contributions follow established dissemination workflows within the scientific community.

Where applicable:

- Publications are made available via open-access routes in compliance with Horizon Europe requirements
- Associated materials (e.g. conference presentations or posters) may be deposited in Zenodo, subject to the decision of the respective first authors
- References to publications and related materials are linked via the project website and Knowledge Hub

This workflow ensures visibility, citability, and long-term accessibility of scientific outputs.

10.3 Workflow for events and meetings

Communication and dissemination activities are coordinated around relevant events, including conferences, workshops, stakeholder meetings, and project-organised events.

Typical workflows include:

- Pre-event communication to announce participation or contributions
- Dissemination of results during events through presentations, posters, or discussions
- Post-event communication to share outcomes, materials, or key messages via the website, LinkedIn, and mailing lists

This approach supports continuity and maximises the impact of event-related activities.

10.4 Workflow for field activities

Field activities represent key components of BioGeoSea's work and are communicated selectively to ensure relevance and clarity.

Where appropriate:

- Information on upcoming cruises or field campaigns is shared in advance
- Selected updates or highlights are communicated during activities
- Post-cruise communication focuses on objectives, methods, and emerging results rather than operational details

This workflow ensures transparency while maintaining a clear focus on scientific relevance.

10.5 Workflow for visual and outreach materials

Visual and outreach materials, including videos and flyers, are developed in coordination with the responsible partners and communication leads.

The workflow includes:

- Definition of objectives, target audiences, and key messages
- Internal review to ensure scientific accuracy and consistency with project messaging
- Publication via the project website and promotion through appropriate communication channels

Materials are reused across multiple contexts, such as events, outreach activities, and online dissemination.

10.6 Workflow for stakeholder engagement and policy feedback

Engagement with stakeholders and policy processes is coordinated at project level to ensure consistent, timely, and representative input.

The BioGeoSea coordinator or Steering Committee provides consolidated feedback on behalf of the consortium on relevant European and international initiatives, such as the European Ocean Observation Initiative, the European Ocean Act, and the European Ocean Research and Innovation Strategy. Input from consortium partners is collected, synthesised, and communicated through appropriate channels.

Stakeholder-related communication and dissemination activities follow a dedicated stakeholder engagement strategy, which is described in a separate project deliverable (Deliverable D1.1 - Stakeholder engagement strategy). This strategy provides detailed guidance on stakeholder identification, engagement formats, and feedback mechanisms and complements the workflows described in this section.

10.7 Coordination and quality assurance

Communication and dissemination activities in BioGeoSea are coordinated by the responsible project manager, who also serves as co-lead of Work Package 5 "European leadership, exploitation, and legacy". This role ensures coherence between communication, dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and long-term impact objectives.

While coordination and quality assurance are managed centrally, the content for communication and dissemination activities is provided by the involved project partners. Communication and dissemination are therefore considered a consortium-wide effort, with contributions reflecting the diversity of expertise and activities across the project.

Activities are aligned with the project's vision, mission, and key messages and comply with Horizon Europe requirements, including visibility, open access, and compliance with applicable data protection regulations (e.g. GDPR).

The coordination of communication and dissemination is closely linked to the project's exploitation strategy, which is described in dedicated deliverables on key exploitable results (Deliverable D5.2 - Draft Exploitation Plan and D5.6 - Final Exploitation Plan). This ensures consistency between dissemination activities and the identification, development, and potential uptake of project results beyond the project lifetime.

11 Monitoring and evaluation

Monitoring and evaluation activities are used to assess the effectiveness of BioGeoSea's communication and dissemination strategy and to support continuous improvement throughout the project lifetime. The focus is on tracking reach, engagement, and uptake in a pragmatic and proportionate manner.

11.1 Monitoring of communication activities

Communication activities are monitored using quantitative and qualitative metrics that reflect visibility and engagement across public-facing channels.

Key metrics include:

- Website usage statistics (e.g., page views, downloads of materials, access to the Knowledge Hub)
- Social media metrics on LinkedIn (e.g., impressions, engagement rates, interactions)
- Distribution and uptake of outreach materials such as videos and flyers
- Participation and feedback at events and outreach activities

These metrics provide insights into how effectively BioGeoSea communicates its objectives, progress, and relevance to broader audiences. Where identifiable, broader external uptake of project information (e.g. references on external websites) may also be noted, without constituting systematic media monitoring.

11.2 Monitoring of dissemination activities

Dissemination activities are monitored with a focus on uptake, reuse, and integration of project results by expert and stakeholder communities.

Key metrics include:

- Number and type of public deliverables and selected milestones published
- Deposits in Zenodo, including assigned DOIs and download statistics
- Scientific publications and conference contributions

- Use of BioGeoSea results in external reports, assessments, or initiatives where identifiable

Monitoring focuses on the relevance and reach of outputs rather than on purely quantitative metrics.

11.3 Evaluation and adaptive improvement

Monitoring results are reviewed periodically by the responsible project manager in coordination with the project coordinator and relevant work package leads. Based on these reviews, adjustments may be made to communication and dissemination activities, channels, or workflows to improve effectiveness and better address target audiences. In addition, indicative internal targets may be defined and adjusted during the project lifetime to support planning and evaluation, without constituting binding performance indicators.

Feedback from the Advisory and Foresight Committee, stakeholders, partners, and external audiences is considered as an important qualitative input to the evaluation process.

11.4 Reporting

Monitoring results are summarised in periodic project reports and relevant deliverables, providing transparency towards the European Commission and supporting accountability within the consortium.

12 Risk management

Effective communication and dissemination require awareness of potential risks that may affect visibility, engagement, or uptake of project results. BioGeoSea addresses these risks through proactive planning, coordination, and adaptive workflows.

12.1 Identification of key risks

The main risks related to communication and dissemination activities include:

- Limited visibility or engagement with communication outputs due to information overload or competing initiatives in the ocean observing landscape.
- Delays in the availability of results or deliverables, which may affect the timing of dissemination activities.
- Complexity of scientific content, making it challenging to communicate key messages to non-expert audiences, including the risk of oversimplification or misinterpretation of indicator results in policy contexts.
- Inconsistent messaging across partners or channels if activities are not sufficiently coordinated.
- Restrictions related to data sensitivity, intellectual property, or policy processes, which may limit what can be shared publicly.

12.2 Mitigation measures

To address these risks, BioGeoSea applies the following mitigation measures:

- Use of clearly defined key messages and audience-specific communication to increase relevance and clarity.

- Selective communication of milestones and results, focusing on those with added value for external audiences.
- Close coordination between the responsible project manager, the project coordinator, and work package leads to ensure consistency and quality.
- Use of multiple complementary channels (website, Zenodo, LinkedIn, newsletters, events) to reach different audiences.
- Internal review processes to ensure compliance with data protection, open access, and Horizon Europe visibility requirements.

12.3 Adaptive management

Risk management is treated as an ongoing process. Communication and dissemination activities are reviewed regularly, and mitigation measures are adapted where necessary based on monitoring results, partner feedback, and external developments.

This adaptive approach ensures that BioGeoSea remains responsive to changing conditions while maintaining effective and responsible communication throughout the project lifecycle.

13 Conclusion

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy provides a structured and coherent framework for ensuring the visibility, understanding, and uptake of BioGeoSea's activities and results throughout the project lifetime. By clearly defining objectives, key messages, target audiences, channels, workflows, and monitoring approaches, the strategy supports effective engagement across scientific, policy, industrial, and societal contexts.

Communication and dissemination in BioGeoSea are implemented as a coordinated, consortium-wide effort, guided by the project's vision, mission, and key messages. The strategy balances transparency and accessibility with targeted dissemination of validated results, ensuring relevance for diverse audiences while maintaining scientific integrity.

Through adaptive management and close coordination with stakeholders, sister projects, and the European Commission, BioGeoSea will continuously refine its communication and dissemination activities. This approach supports not only the project's immediate impact but also its long-term contribution to biogeochemical ocean observing, European leadership, and sustainable ocean management beyond the project duration.